

“ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE AND HUMAN RIGHTS IN PAKISTAN: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF ARTICLE 9A AND INTERNATIONAL TREATY OBLIGATIONS.”

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Abstract

The constitutionalization of the "Right to a Healthy Environment" in Pakistan under Article 9A represents a key constitutional advancement, affirming environmental protection as a constitutional duty. This positions Pakistan among the few nations with justiciable environmental rights and clarifies governmental roles in protecting natural resources. The ruling identifies illegal tree cutting as a violation of Articles 9 and 9A, affecting sustainability. However, challenges such as institutional weaknesses and political inertia may render Article 9A symbolic without robust legal support. The study highlights the gap between Pakistan's environmental policies and international human rights standards, stressing a lack of a human rights perspective and superficial compliance measures toward vulnerable communities. It underscores the contribution of Article 9A to scholarship and the reporting cycle of human rights treaty bodies.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation is one of Pakistan's biggest governance and human rights issues. Accelerated urban growth, inadequate regulatory frameworks, industrial pollutants, groundwater pollution, and frequent climate-related disasters have caused a multifaceted environmental crisis that affects public health, livelihoods, and socioeconomic stability. Pakistan is one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change, which causes recurring floods, heatwaves, drought cycles, and agricultural ecosystem degradation. It needs a coherent set of legal and governance amendments, including emergency

response and long-term policy, in light of rights-based constitutional protections. After the 26th Constitutional Amendment, Article 9A, which constitutionalized the right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment, shifted the policy-based to right-based protection. This right is constitutionalized due to consistent UN Human Rights treaty bodies' reports, international Human Rights obligations, and public interest litigation at the national level, where the higher judiciary set several favorable precedents and included the right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment.

Before the 26th Amendment, environmental rights were only judicially interpreted under the Article 9 and 14. Shehla Zia case is the foundation of environmental rights, and Leghari case, the right to life was expanded to include environmental protections and climate agitation. Inserting the right to clean, healthy, and sustainable environment filled the doctrinal gap but opened a right-based access, fulfilment, and security to such right, which requires a robust implementation, execution procedure, administrative coherence, and compliance with Pakistan's international human-rights obligations. Weak enforcement mechanisms, institutional fragmentation, and inconsistent policy execution show that environmental rights are still not fully realized in the constitution.

Since Pakistan is a signatory to seven UN human-rights treaties, including the ICCPR, ICESCR, CRC, CEDAW, CERD, CAT, and CRPD, their reports provide international jurisprudence on strengthening environmental rights in the constitutional and policy domain and overcoming the game between such rights and their realization and public impact. These treaties require the right to life, health, water, an adequate standard of living, non-discrimination, accessibility, and protection of vulnerable groups, which are closely linked to climate change and environmental justice. In response to Pakistan's latest reports to treaty bodies, the committees' concluding reports, specifically the ICCPR, ICESCR, and CRC, praised the adoption measures for climate change and environmental protection but criticized the shortfalls and urged Pakistan to do more and raise the standard of the measures adopted as per international standards as and when required. As reported by treaty bodies in their concluding reports, Pakistan's state reports to the concerned committees did not address Article 9A's direct role in shifting from judicial interpretation to environmental constitutionalism.

This disconnect highlights the primary research issue of this study: despite the constitutional enhancement of environmental rights through Article 9A and Pakistan's significant international human rights commitments, a notable gap persists between normative guarantees and their execution—both domestically and within the treaty-body reporting framework.

Primarily this research will shed light on the following: (i) to analyze the doctrinal scope and implications of Article 9A within Pakistan's constitutional framework; (ii) to evaluate the environmental components of Pakistan's obligations under core human-rights treaties; (iii) to examine the extent to which recent state reports and treaty-body concluding observations address environmental justice; and (iv) to identify institutional, legal, and policy gaps that hinder effective implementation of Article 9A. In pursuit of these objectives, this study addresses the following research questions:

This research is mainly based on doctrinal legal research methodology i.e. constitutional interpretation, case laws analysis, and scrutiny of domestic environmental legislation, also there is comparison of other countries, international standards and domestic law and policy in term of environment and climate change. Out of total, three i.e. ICCPR, ICESCR and CRC treaty-body review method is adopted to check the state reports of Pakistan and concluding observations of the treaty bodies to get the lens and approach of international oversight mechanisms deal with environmental justice and climate change issues. Environmental judicial activism and constitutionalism in Pakistan is examined comprehensively within both the domestic and international legal systems through this method.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE AND HUMAN RIGHTS

Environmental justice is moral and legal. It aims to treat all people equally, regardless of race, gender, or socioeconomic status, by providing environmental protections like fair distributions of environmental benefits, access to public and stakeholder opinion, and highlighting the importance of a safe environment for human rights under domestic and international law. These principles underpin environmental constitutionalism and Pakistan's Article 9A. Environmental protection is dependent on all other human rights as settled International jurisprudence and states are under obligation to make sure the protection of environmental rights. United Nations General Assembly adopted the resolution in which human right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment is recognized, confirms that environmental degradation, climate change, and

pollution hinder the enjoyment of the rights to life, health, food, water, housing, and a sufficient standard of living. It emphasizes procedural rights including access to information and participation in governance, promoting transparency and accountability, and is supported by international organizations for its relevance to various rights, especially for vulnerable groups. Pakistan also ratified the above treaty and duty bound to three essential obligations: to respect, protect, and fulfil human rights pertaining to the environment, prominently adding Article 9A to the constitution is one step towards fulfilling the obligation, followed by institutional reforms and funds allocation in budget. International human rights law positioned that there is strong connection between environmental conditions in enjoying all other human rights as the UNHRC recognized that the ability of current and future generations to exercise their right to life is seriously threatened by environmental degradation and climate change. It stresses that states must take steps to reduce environmental risks that could endanger life. Safeguarding the environment is crucial for the fulfilment of fundamental human rights, encompassing the rights to life, right to clean healthy and sustainable environment, dignity, water, and sanitation. Environmental degradation jeopardizes these rights by undermining the essential conditions for survival and well-being. Essential points encompass: the right to life is jeopardized by environmental threats such as pollution and climate change; the right to health is compromised by unsanitary conditions resulting in disease; human dignity is diminished by residing in polluted and hazardous environments; access to clean water is obstructed by pollution and excessive extraction; and adequate housing is adversely affected by environmental catastrophes and unsafe living conditions.

Apart from international jurisprudence, regional courts of human-rights also interpret the environmental rights included in the right to life. One of the regional court held that the right to a healthy environment is an autonomous human right essential for the enjoyment of all other rights. Such opinion affirmed the ecological obligations of states and the concept of environmental harm as a violation of human dignity. The European Court of Human

Rights has made it clear that damage to the environment is a violation of the rights to private life, family life, and life under the European Convention on Human Rights. These choices show that protecting the environment and protecting human rights go hand in hand, especially when it comes to pollution, dangerous industries, and the government's failure to regulate. The UN Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and the Environment has also made clear what states must do, such as creating laws to protect the environment, enforcing those laws, making sure people have access to information and protecting communities that are more affected by environmental damages than others. In sum, it demonstrates that environmental protection is integral to broader human-rights guarantees, both internationally and within Pakistan's constitutional structure. This framework not only supports a holistic understanding of Article 9A but also places Pakistan's environmental responsibilities squarely within established and emerging norms of international human-rights jurisprudence.

EVOLUTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONSTITUTIONALISM IN PAKISTAN JUDICIAL FOUNDATIONS OF ENVIRONMENTAL RIGHTS (PRE-ARTICLE 9A)

In absence of any statutory law for environmental rights, the Pakistan judiciary stepped to affirm the right to a healthy environment under the Article 9 right to life and Article 14 right to dignity in the foundational case of the environmental rights where the Superior laid down the liberal interpretation of right to life with dignity and affirm the right to a healthy environment is a fundamental right and established the principle of that human life cannot be understood independently from environmental quality. It became the cornerstone of environmental jurisprudence in Pakistan. The Khewra Mines case examined the critical issue of water accessibility and contamination, underscoring its importance in relation to the right to life. The Supreme Court explicitly acknowledged that in circumstances of limited, difficult, or restricted access to water, the right to clean and uncontaminated water is fundamentally linked to the right to life. The Lahore High Court (LHC) in the case reasoned that the protection of the environment was an inalienable

right and perhaps more fundamental than the other rights within the framework of constitutional rights. Significant judicial progress has emerged from these proactive interpretations, especially in cases led by public interest and human rights organizations. For instance, farmers in the Ravi Urban Development Authority area have successfully preserved land rights for food security, while environmental activists halted the destruction of the Lahore canal's green cover, leading to Supreme Court intervention and the Lahore Canal Heritage Park Act 2013. The Lahore High Court in another case, highlighted the urgency of adapting to climate change and the judiciary's role in fostering climate awareness for social and environmental justice, and order for standing committee on climate change. In more recent case, the Supreme Court prohibited the establishment and expansion of cement plants in environmentally fragile zones, stressing the significance of incorporating climate change considerations into government decisions and policies concerning vital issues such as water management in Pakistan. Before the insertion of Article 9A, lastly, the Supreme Court in the case issued an order which emphasised the importance of incorporating climate change considerations into urban planning processes, recognising that the impacts of climate change on cities directly affect the fundamental rights of the residents, including the right to life, dignity, and property. After the introduction of Article 9A to the Constitution, the Supreme Court acknowledged that a life worth living includes a sustainable environment, now mandated by the Constitution. Collectively, these cases demonstrate an evolving judicial understanding that environmental harm is fundamentally incompatible with constitutional rights.

LEGISLATIVE AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

Prior to Article 9A's inclusion in the Constitution, the right to a clean and healthy environment was inferred from court rulings. Although Pakistan's first environmental legislation dates back to 1983, it largely remained inactive, with the relevant institutions not effectively established. The federal legislatures for the first time enacted the law related to the environmental protection, guaranteed that environmental protection, conservation, rehabilitation, and enhancement initiatives were optimized, and

sustainable development was advocated. It also provided an environmental tribunal grievance redress mechanism to execute the law's mandate. The 18th Amendment to the Constitution abolished the Concurrent List, transferring environmental regulatory authority to the provinces. Each province enacted its own environmental laws based on the Pakistan Environmental Protection Act (PEPA), with provincial environmental protection agencies (EPAs) as the main regulators. However, the effectiveness of the EPAs has been questioned by the judiciary and civil society, as evidenced by cases Asghar Leghari case, Signal-Free Corridor case, Haroon Farooq and Maple Leaf Cement Company highlighting poor air quality, water and food security challenges, and inadequate disaster management in major cities.

In 2017, Pakistan enacted the Climate Change Act, establishing the Pakistan Climate Change Council and the Pakistan Climate Change Authority, tasked with formulating climate policies and coordinating climate initiatives. Still, even with this forward-thinking framework, execution isn't always effective. Provincial environmental agencies, which were created by the 18th Amendment, have trouble with capacity, coordination, and compliance. These changes to the law show that institutions are aware of environmental issues, but they also show that there are still differences between the law and how it is actually put into practice.

CONSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION THROUGH ARTICLE 9A

Pakistan was the nation hit hardest by severe weather in 2022, according to the Climate Risk Index (CRI) 2025. After years of thick and thin struggles, both judicially and constitutionally, despite the in-out of martial laws, even the tug of war between military establishment versus civilian rule, Pakistan finally constitutionalized the right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment after seventy-eight years of independence. The present constitutionalized right is secured due after decades of judicial activism and historically superior courts most of the time upheld such right and indicated to have a right back by constitutional force. It establishes a constitutional foundation for judicial and executive action on this right, treating its protection as a constitutional duty rather than an activist agenda. The bench,

acknowledged Pakistan's environmental vulnerability and confirmed that the newly enacted Article 9A establishes the "Right to a Healthy Environment" as an independent constitutional right, distinct from Article 9. This landmark ruling represents the first judicial application of Article 9A, positioning Pakistan among a select few nations with such a right in their constitution, thereby making environmental rights justiciable. The judgment also clarifies the responsibilities of government authorities in protecting natural resources, asserting that illegal tree cutting by the Forest Department violates Article 9 and 9A, adversely impacting environmental sustainability. Additionally, it paves the way for future Public Interest Litigation (PIL) pertaining to environmental rights, setting a precedent for subsequent judicial decisions. Institutional weaknesses, insufficient political will, and bureaucratic obstacles impede the effective implementation of Article 9A in Pakistan. In the absence of strong regulatory frameworks and efficient policy implementation, the article's importance may be purely symbolic and inadequate in confronting the nation's environmental crisis as rightly point out by HRC report. Its efficacy depends on supplementary legislation, administrative dedication, and incorporation into national planning.

PAKISTAN'S INTERNATIONAL HUMAN-RIGHTS OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO THE ENVIRONMENT

Pakistan has ratified seven out of the nine principal UN human rights treaties. Each of these treaties contains provisions regarding environmental protection, redress for ecological harm, and the rights of communities adversely affected by environmental degradation. The state's periodic reports and the treaty bodies' concluding observations provide insight into Pakistan's management of environmental issues, or lack thereof, throughout its reporting cycle, but last state reports and concluding reports are not in light of Article 9A, due to timing of reports and 26th constitutional Amendment.

INTERNATIONAL COVENANT ON CIVIL AND POLITICAL RIGHTS (ICCPR)

The Human Rights Committee, in December 2024, in the concluding observations on the second periodic report of Pakistan in paragraph 20 of Climate Change

endorsed the implementation of initiatives including the Pakistan Climate Change Act of 2017 and the Pakistan National Adaptation Plan of 2023. Nonetheless, it is apprehensive about the detrimental effects of pollution, environmental degradation, climate change, and natural disasters on the enjoyment of human rights particularly the right to life of the population, especially rural communities and marginalized groups that have been disproportionately impacted by severe flooding. But the Committee expressed regret over the insufficient information regarding sustainable policies implemented by the State party to safeguard individuals, particularly the most vulnerable, from the effects of environmental degradation and climate change.

In paragraph 21, the Committee ask for do more from Pakistan by stating that in accordance with Article 6 of the Covenant and in light of the Committee's General Comment on the right to life, the State party should enhance its efforts to alleviate the effects of climate change and environmental degradation, establish a sustainable prevention policy framework, and ensure its effective implementation alongside the legal framework, particularly concerning disaster prevention. Additionally, it should take appropriate measures to adopt a precautionary approach to safeguard individuals from the adverse impacts of environmental degradation, climate change, and natural disasters. Addressing environmental factors is crucial for life, health, and safety. The document emphasizes the need for stricter regulations on industries responsible for air and water pollution and calls for the protection of communities affected by climate-induced displacement. It also highlights the lack of a rights-based environmental governance framework that connects environmental degradation to civil and political rights.

The ICCPR does not explicitly acknowledge environmental rights; however, the UN Human Rights Committee (HRC) has unequivocally determined that environmental degradation can infringe upon Article 6 (right to life), Article 7 (prohibition of inhuman treatment), and Article 17 (privacy, home, and family).

INTERNATIONAL COVENANT ON ECONOMIC, SOCIAL AND CULTURAL RIGHTS (ICESCR)

The ICESCR has several articles that are directly related to the environment, such as Articles 11 (adequate standard of living) and 12 (right to health). The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) has consistently asserted that environmental conditions are essential to socio-economic rights. The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in Concluding observations, in July 2017, on the initial report of Pakistan showed great concern on Water and Sanitation in paragraph 73 that in spite of the fact that the Committee acknowledges the progress that the State party has made, it continues to be concerned about the fact that a significant number of people still do not have access to clean drinking water and adequate sanitation facilities. In paragraph 74, it is recommended by the Committee that the State party step up its efforts to expand access to clean drinking water and sanitation facilities that are adequate, including the complete implementation of the National Drinking Water Policy 2009, which was established in 2009.

In follow-up information relating to paragraph 74 of the last concluding observations, the Pakistan submitted the Second periodic report in the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in 2023, where the Pakistan take the position in paragraphs 160-162 that The National Drinking Water Policy of 2009 in Pakistan aims to ensure equitable access to safe drinking water, especially for women, by 2025, alongside the proposed Pakistan Safe Drinking Water Bill for quality compliance. The 2018 water policy package includes a National Water Policy and a Charter that recommends increasing federal investment in the water sector from 3.7% to at least 10% in 2018-19 and 20% by 2030, establishing an apex body for water legislation, and creating a Groundwater Authority and provincial water authorities. This policy incorporates recommendations from the 2009 National Drinking Water Policy and the 2012 National Climate Change Policy to address climate change impacts, enhance water storage through dam construction, rehabilitate infrastructure, manage groundwater abstraction, reduce agricultural water demand, and strengthen water resource management institutions.

CONVENTION ON THE RIGHTS OF THE CHILD (CRC)

Environmental degradation disproportionately impacts children due to exposure to pollution, unsafe water, climate-related disasters, and food insecurity. The Committee on the Rights of the Child lastly in July 2016, published the Concluding observations on the fifth periodic report submitted by Pakistan, in which the Committee shown great concerns in term of Environmental Health stated in the paragraph 57 that the Committee is extremely concerned about the adverse effects that polluted air, water, and soil have on the health of children, as well as the inadequate measures that have been taken to address this challenge. Also the Committee recommended in the paragraph 58 that the state party conduct an evaluation of the impact that polluted air, water, and soil have on the health of children. This evaluation will serve as a foundation for the development of a well-resourced strategy to address the situation and regulate the maximum concentrations of air and water pollutants.

In response, in February 2024, the Pakistan submitted the combined sixth and seventh periodic reports under article 44 of the Convention, which was due in 2021, where in response to paragraph 58 of the last concluding observation related to Environment Health, the state party in paragraph 205 provided that the Government of Pakistan will evaluate the effects of polluted air, water, and soil on the environment. The health of children in order to provide a foundation for the development of a strategy to address such problems. On the other hand, the World Health Organization's Global Health Observatory has estimated that environmental factors in Pakistan are responsible for approximately 200 deaths per 100,000 people.

CRITICAL ANALYSIS: GAPS BETWEEN ARTICLE 9A AND TREATY-BODY EXPECTATIONS

It is true that at the time of submission of the last state's reports in the UN human-rights treaty bodies in February 2024, the Article 9A was not enacted which in fact become part of the Constitution through 26th amendment in October 2024. In spite this, there is a bridge between the treaty body expectations from the Pakistan and state reports due to certain reasons like that of weak execution of the environmental rights provided in the special laws and

not as per international human rights standards. There is also shortcoming in environmental policies as the lens of the human rights are not there to overcome with the committees' concerns as not being right-based but policy-based towards environmental rights. The treaty bodies expect specific measures adopted based on evidence and figures for the vulnerable communities like that of child, who are affected at first and most, but there are only superficial general compliance measures taken by Pakistan and without analytical depth for marginalized environmental justice. Pakistan is also missing a uniform national environmental policy and more specifically after the 18th amendment where the provinces have their own special laws, forums and procedures for redress of environmental issues, limited focus on their specific needs within environmental governance, a national environmental policy is much needed in compliance with the Article 9A. Monitoring and accountability mechanisms are insufficient, with challenges in public access to justice for environmental violations, should provide air and water quality, EIAs climate-risk mapping. After the insertion of Article 9A which guarantee the right to clean, healthy and sustainable environment as fundamental right is evident of the Pakistan commitment to the human rights and right-based approach to climate change and environment. Comparative cases demonstrate that treaty-body engagement can transpire in the absence of explicit constitutional provisions. Countries like South Africa and Colombia have successfully used treaty-body oversight by linking environmental issues to rights discussions. On the other hand, Pakistan's lack of action shows that it missed a chance to follow the rules, not that it was against the law. Article 9A is an important constitutional chance, but if future reports keep ignoring environmental justice, the change might not mean anything. So, real participation by treaty bodies is necessary to keep the promise in the Constitution to protect the environment.

FUTURE-REPORTING STRATEGY FOR PAKISTAN UNDER ARTICLE 9A

In the next state's reports in regard with environmental rights and climate change, Pakistan shall report in the light of the Article 9A as the environmental judicial interpretation now shifted to

the environmental constitutionalism and with this the shifting to right-based from policy-based environmental reporting. Such constitutional guaranteed rights under Article 9A shall be integrated in all state reports into treaty reporting cycles for all relevant conventions specifically to the ICCPR, ICESCR and CRC, where there are concerns of the committees and asked for do more from Pakistan. In future state's reports, fixed facts, figures and specific measures taken by the state, not limited to laws enacted but environmental inspections, shall be included as per expectations of the committees, and provide the environmental data related to the enforcement action taken of such rights under Article 9A through executive and judiciary by mentioning the decided cases, remedies granted, pending and execution stage of the complaints reported before the tribunals, courts, budget allocations and hurdles in such enforcements. In coming reports there is also need of timely reporting as till now there is delay in state reports submission before the committees, this can enhance the performance of the state and timely reduce the concerns of the treaty bodies. For this, there is need of strong follow-up mechanism on environment having a special cell at the ministry of Human Rights and each provincial tribunal and central monitoring system by providing yearly compliance reports in coordination with all concerned ministries, tribunals, organizations and local bodies if any.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The environmental crisis in Pakistan is a critical issue encompassing governance and human rights, worsened by urban growth, regulatory inadequacies, and climate change. The recent constitutional amendment via the 26th Amendment formalized the right to a clean, healthy environment under Article 9A, spurred by UN reports and judicial precedents that previously interpreted these rights under the right to life. Despite this advancement, significant gaps remain in the enforcement of these rights, with institutional fragmentation and weak policies obstructing realization. Pakistan, a signatory to multiple UN human rights treaties, faces calls to enhance its environmental rights standards, yet still struggles with the practical implementation of these constitutional rights, as highlighted in reports to

treaty bodies. Consequently, a disconnect persists between the constitutional recognition of environmental rights and their actual enforcement, presenting a core challenge for the nation. Achieving this integration necessitates a strategic approach that combines constitutional law, administrative reforms, and international human-rights standards.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

LEGISLATIVE REFORMS TO OPERATIONALIZE ARTICLE 9A

The present environmental laws are out-date after the 26th Constitutional Amendment and need to be revise, cross check, amended or repeal in the light of the Article 9A. The main statutes along with all other acts, ordinances, rules and regulations to be updated as per constitutional right to environment in the light of concluding observations of human rights treaty bodies. The power granted to magistrates of environmental tribunals shall be enhance and punishment shall change to a rigorous one so may deterrence at maximum. There should also be extra heavy penalties depending upon heinousness of the wrong done. There should also be special trainings for the officers of environmental institutions to understand the importance of such right in which future of an agricultural country is associated, and one technical officer shall be appointed for examinations and testing purposes.

INSTITUTIONAL STRENGTHENING AND INTER-AGENCY COORDINATION

Environmental institutions like Environmental Protection Agencies (EPAs) and Environmental Tribunals are not strengthened enough and need to be delegated with power to make sure the enforcement independently and speedily. Such institutions shall be independent of bureaucracy and political pressures and shall treat all parties as same as all citizens are equal before law. The number of labs for tests are less in number as per number of the industries in Pakistan with limited resources and funding. There is also need of strong and systematic coordination between the agencies which can overcome the delay in proceedings and the proceedings shall be summary in nature. To make this

stronger, there needs to be clear lines of authority and coordination between agencies.

INTEGRATING PROCEDURAL ENVIRONMENTAL RIGHTS

The CESC and HRC treaty bodies stress how important procedural rights are for environmental justice. Pakistan can fulfil its constitutional and international obligations by establishing a public digital database for environmental information, promoting community involvement in environmental decision-making, and enhancing access to remedies through legal aid and streamlined procedures. These steps would make Article 9A a real constitutional protection for environmental rights.

DEVELOP A NATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE POLICY

In the presence of Article 9A which is the constitutional shield for climate change and environmental rights, there is need of national policy to deal with environmental and climate changes issues, a uniform policy in the light of right-based approach to clean, healthy and sustainable environment. This shall help in environmental governance, execution of environmental rights and a uniform and harmonized inter-provincial coordination, as the present environmental policy is policy-based and without the constitutional backup and guaranteed fundamental right. Nevertheless, this shall incorporate the concluding observations of UN human-rights treaty bodies into such national policy planning and establish a national follow-up mechanism for treaty-body recommendations.

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